

SYNTHESIS AND STRUCTURE OF THE COCRYSTAL BETWEEN CU(II) COMPLEX OF SALICYLIC ACID AND UNCOORDINATED PIRACETAM

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Cocrystals, formed between an active pharmaceutical ingredient (API) and a cocrystal former, are attracting increasing interest within the pharmaceutical community as a promising alternative for solid drug formation. To date, scientists have synthesized numerous types of uncommon cocrystals containing metal complexes as crystal formers and APIs [1-3]. These cocrystals offer enhancements to various pharmaceutically relevant properties compared to single-component crystals, including solubility, dissolution rate, hydration stability, fluorescence performance, and bioavailability [4]. In this work, we synthesized a cocrystal based on salicylic acid and piracetam, determined its structure as well.

For synthesizing, 0.276 g (2 mmol) of 2-hydroxybenzoic acid was dissolved completely in 30 ml of ethanol through stirring. Subsequently, a solution of 0.142 g (1 mmol) of 2-oxo-1-pyrrolidine acetamide in 10 ml of ethanol was poured into the previously mentioned solution and thoroughly mixed. The resulting solution was then slowly added to a solution of 0.2 g (1 mmol) copper acetate monohydrate in 20 ml of water, during stirring. The resulting solution was placed in a thermostat at a constant temperature of 22 °C. After 11 days, green crystals were formed with a yield of 72% (0.31 mg). Elemental analysis for C₃₄H₃₄Cu₂O₁₆N₂ (854 gr/mol): calcd. C 47.77 %; O 30.0 %; H 4.0 %; N 3.28 %; found: C 45.83 %; O 28.96 %; H 4.2 %; N 3.32 %.

The asymmetric part of the unit cell consists of three fragments (Fig. 1a). They are halves of the two complex molecules and one piracetam (2-(2-oxopyrrolidin-1-yl)acetamide) molecule because complex molecules are located on inversion centers while uncoordinated piracetam molecule occupies total position of the unit cell (Fig. 1b). Both complex molecules are in the form of “Chinese lantern” in which symmetry centers are located between Cu(II) ions. The dimeric Cu1 and Cu2 ions of the independent complex molecules I and II chelate four salicylic acid molecules through oxygen atoms of the carboxylate group and coordinate two water molecules. Oxygen atoms O2, O3, O5 and O6 of the molecule I (atoms O8, O9, O11 and O12 for molecule II) are in equatorial positions while oxygen atom O15 (O16 for molecule II) of the water molecule occupies axial position [4]. Bond lengths of equatorial atoms are in the range of 1.954-1.984 Å whereas bond distances of axial atoms are 2.120 and 2.106 Å due to Jahn-Teller effect.

Fig. 1. Asymmetry unit (a) and ORTEP structure (b) of the cocrystal (hydrogen atoms are omitted for clarity, and the thermal ellipsoids are drawn at the 30% probability level).

Literature

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